

Polarographic Estimation of Copper-, Lead- and Zinc(II) in Presence of 2,3-Dihydroxypyridine as Complexing Agent

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2,3-Dihydroxypyridine had been used for the spectrophotometric determination of Fe^{I} and Os^{2} , polarographic determination of Yb^{3} and the stability constants of In^{I} , Tl^{5} and Eu^{6} complexes with DHP have been evaluated polarographically. In the present work, the polarographic characteristics of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} in presence of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) have been investigated and conditions suggested for the determination of these metal ions individually and in the presence of each other. The procedure developed has been applied to the determination of copper and to the simultaneous determination of lead and zinc in certain ores.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH : The polarograms of the solution containing 1 mM of Cu^{II} or Pb^{II} or Zn^{II} and 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (0.1 mM) were recorded at various pH values and a well-defined wave was obtained in the pH range 9.5–12.0. The diffusion current did not change in this pH range. Hence, this pH range was chosen to study the polarographic behaviour of these metal-DHP complexes.

Effect of mercury pressure : Polarograms of the metal ion (0.1 mM) and DHP solution (0.1 M) were recorded at various heights of the mercury column. The linear dependence of the limiting current on the square-root of the mercury column indicated that the rate of reduction of the metal-DHP complex was a diffusion-controlled process.

Effect of [DHP] : The shape of the wave did not change when the [DHP] was increased from

1 to 4 mM. The formation of the complex was evident as the half-wave potential became more negative with increasing concentration of DHP (Table 1). The value of diffusion current for reduction of metals ions in the presence of ligand was smaller than in its absence, proving larger size of the complexed ion. The plots of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ (potential of the dropping electrode) is a straight line for all the three systems. The values of the slopes and half-wave potentials for various concentrations of DHP are given in Table 1. The slopes of semi-log plots reveal that two-electron reversible reduction took place in the case of Cu-DHP and Pb-DHP complexes but the wave was quasi-reversible in case of Zn-DHP complex.

Effect of metal ion concentration : Polarograms over the concentration ranges 0.10–0.30 mM of Cu^{II} , 0.05–0.25 mM of Pb^{II} and 0.10–0.30 mM Zn^{II} were recorded in the presence of 1 mM of DHP, 0.1 M KNO_3 and 0.002% gelatin at pH 10.0. The diffusion currents were measured by the extrapolation method and calibration curves constructed. The diffusion current increased linearly in each case, which confirmed that the waves were diffusion-controlled. Hence, the polarographic results can be used for their quantitative determination.

Recommended procedure for the determination of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} : Calibration curve was prepared for each of the metals by recording the polarogram of the metals at various concentrations. The diffusion current values of the polarograms were plotted against the concentration of the metal ion. To determine

the metal ion content in an unknown solution polarogram was recorded under identical conditions.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF LIGAND CONCENTRATION IN Cu^{II} -, Pb^{II} - AND Zn^{II} - DHP COMPLEX SYSTEMS

$[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}]$, $[\text{Pb}^{\text{II}}]$ or $[\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.1 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M (KNO}_3)$
 $h = 45 \text{ cm}$, pH (NH₃/NH₄Cl buffer) = 10.0, maximum suppressor 0.002% gelatin

Sl no	[DHP] mM	i_d μA	$E_{1/2}$ (V vs SCE)	Slope of log plot
Cu ^{II} -DHP system				
1	0	1.40	0.230	30
2	1	0.75	0.235	29
3	2	0.75	0.235	32
4	3	0.75	0.240	30
5	4	0.75	0.240	31
Pb ^{II} -DHP system				
1	0	1.10	0.410	31
2	1	0.70	0.490	30
3	2	0.70	0.560	32
4	3	0.70	0.580	32
5	4	0.70	0.590	31
Zn ^{II} -DHP system				
1	0	0.90	1.300	42
2	1	0.60	1.320	43
3	2	0.60	1.325	42
4	3	0.60	1.330	40
5	4	0.60	1.335	41

The diffusion current value was obtained and the corresponding concentration of the metal ion in the solution was determined from the linear calibration plot. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} AND Zn^{II} WITH DHP

[DHP] = 1 mM, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M (KNO}_3)$, $h = 45 \text{ cm}$, pH (NH₃/NH₄Cl buffer) = 10.0, maximum suppressor 0.002% gelatin

Sl no	Metal	Amount of metal (mg)	
		Taken	Found
Copper			
1		0.079	0.078
2		0.119	0.118
3		0.158	0.158
4		0.198	0.199
Lead			
1		0.155	0.154
2		0.233	0.232
3		0.310	0.310
4		0.388	0.387
Zinc			
1		0.082	0.081
2		0.123	0.124
3		0.164	0.163
4		0.204	0.204

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of various anions and cations at a fixed concentration of copper, lead and zinc (1 mM) with 0.1 M DHP was ascertained. In the presence of nitrate, sulphate, acetate and formate, the half-wave potential values remained almost constant in all cases.

Among the metal ions examined only Pb^{II} and Fe^{III} interfered while Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} did not interfere upto 10-fold excess in the polarographic determination of copper. Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} interfered, while Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ba^{II} and Mn^{II} did not interfere upto 5-fold excess in the polarographic determination of lead. Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} interfered while Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Bi^{III} could be tolerated upto 5-fold excess in the determination of Zn^{II}.

Mixed polarograms of Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} : From the individual polarograms of Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} it is possible to differentiate the two metal ions in the DHP solution as their half-wave potentials differed by more than 0.8 V. Consequently, a series of polarograms were recorded with synthetically mixed solutions of the two metal ions and the diffusion current values measured for each metal ions were referred to the respective calibration curves and the metal ion concentration was calculated (Table 3).

TABLE 3—SIMULTANEOUS POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF Pb^{II} AND Zn^{II} WITH DHP

[DHP] = 1 mM, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M (KNO}_3)$, $h = 45 \text{ cm}$, pH (NH₃/NH₄Cl buffer) = 10.0, maximum suppressor 0.002% gelatin

Sl no	Amount of metal added (mg)		Amount of metal found (mg)	
	Pb	Zn	Pb	Zn
1	0.155	0.082	0.155	0.081
2	0.233	0.123	0.234	0.123
3	0.310	0.164	0.309	0.164
4	0.388	0.204	0.387	0.203

Determination of Cu in ore : The proposed method was applied for estimation of Cu in ore sample collected from Khetri Copper Complex, Rajasthan. A powdered sample (0.1 g) of the ore was mixed with 5% Br₂ solution (10 ml) in CCl₄. The beaker was covered and after 1 h, concentrated HNO₃ (5 ml) was added and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. Bromine and CCl₄ were expelled by gentle heating, then cooled, and 50% (v/v) H₂SO₄ (5 ml) and HF (20 ml) were

added and the solution was allowed to evaporate to incipient dryness to ensure removal of HF. After cooling, aqua regia (20 ml) was added and heated gently on a hot-plate at $\sim 60^\circ$ for 1 h. The volume was then reduced to about 10 ml and the solution was filtered and the filtrate was made upto 100 ml. The solution (1 ml) used in the determination contained about 0.15 mg of copper. The results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} IN JRE

Sl no	Values found % Cu	Mean value % Cu	Accepted value*	Standard deviation	Error %
1	14.21				
2	14.45				
3	14.52	14.23	14.27	+0.25	0.28
4	14.99				
5	13.98				

*Values by atomic absorption spectrometry and titrimetric method

Simultaneous determination of Pb and Zn in ore: The present method was successfully applied for the simultaneous determination of lead and zinc in ore sample collected from Deri Deposit, Rajasthan. The method for the decomposition of ore was exactly the same as stated before. The results obtained are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—SIMULTANEOUS POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF Pb^{II} AND Zn^{II} IN ORE

Values found (%)		Mean value (%)		Accepted value* (%)	
Pb	Zn	Pb	Zn	Pb	Zn
15.70	16.34				
15.77	15.82				
15.16	16.06	15.58	16.09	15.61	16.16
15.47	16.40				
15.80	15.83				

*Values by atomic absorption spectrometry method
Standard deviation for Pb and Zn, +0.27; % error for Pb = 0.16, Zn = 0.43.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their stock solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. KNO_3 solution was used to keep the ionic strength constant at 0.1 M. Gelatin solution (0.002%) was used to eliminate the polarographic maxima. Ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer was prepared. Triple-distilled mercury was used for dropping mercury electrode (DME).

Experiments were carried out using a PAR 174A manual polarographic analyser coupled with potentiostat/galvanostat (model 173) to obtain current-voltage curves. A three-electrode system DME, SCE and Pt wire (CE) was used. Oxygen was expelled by bubbling argon gas through the test solution for about 15 min. The capillary characteristics of DME were, $m = 2.762 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$; $t = 4.0 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.48 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at $h = 45 \text{ cm}$ in 0.1 M KNO_3 solution (in open-circuit). The polarograms were recorded at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

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